

Line Tracing Car (Simulation) by Using V-REP

Prepared By

Md Shakib Hasan (韩文韬)

Electronic Information Engineering

China West Normal University (西华师范大学)

shakib.hasan17nov@gmail.com

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Car Tracing Design and Simulation

Abstract:

Line follower robot (LFR) follows a line, and in order to follow a line, robot must detect the line first. Now the question is how to implement the line sensing mechanism in an LFR. We all know that the reflection of light on the white surface is maximum and minimum on the black surface because the black surface absorbs maximum amount of light. So, we are going to use this property of light to detect the line. To detect light, either LDR (light-dependent resistor) or an IR sensor can be used. For this project, we are going with the IR sensor because of its higher accuracy. To detect the line, we place two IR sensors one on the left and other on the right side of the robot as marked in the diagram below. We then place the robot on the line such that the line lies in the middle of both sensors.

Keywords:

Line Follower, Robot, CoppeliaSim, V-REP, Car, Car Mechanism, Working Flow, Algorithm, Component, Control, Tracing, Installation, Experiments, Analysis, Python, C, C++, Program, Code, Simulation, Environment, Parameters, Lua Code, Tool bars, Paths, Module, Sensor, Vision Sensor, Motor, Right Moto, Left Motor, Wheel, Force Sensor, Graph and Scene, Robotics, Autonomous car, Fuzzy control system, Computer vision.

1. Simulation Platform Introduction

From exploring planets to cleaning homes, the reach and versatility of robotics is vast. The integration of actuation, sensing and control makes robotics systems powerful, but complicates their simulation. This paper introduces a versatile, scalable, yet powerful general-purpose robot simulation framework called V-REP. The exponential increase in processing power of computers (not to mention 3D graphics hardware) along with the plethora of open software and hardware standards has drastically changed the landscape in the field of (3D) robotics simulation. Not only has this enabled more complexity on the desktop, but conversely it has provided the ability to run simulations (in real-time) with hardware in-the-loop, or to have mobile/embedded systems controlled from a simulation framework.

1.1 CoppeliaSim (VREP) Software Installation

Step- 1: Download installation file from-

<https://www.coppeliarobotics.com/downloads>

Step- 2: Extract Downloaded File:

Step- 3: Click "Next"

Step- 4: Accept the Term of Installations and Click “Next”

Step- 5: Set Program Shortcut and Click “Next”

Step- 6: Confirm Installing Settings and Click “Next”

Step- 7: The Installing system will copy all important files automatically.

Step- 8: Setup will be completed after completing the setup click “Finish”

Step- 9 (Final Step): After completing the setup, in start menu we will be able to find Coppeliasim Edu shortcut.

1.2 CoppeliaSim (VREP) Simulation Development Environment

V-REP is designed around a versatile architecture. There is no main or central functionality in V-REP. Rather, V-REP possesses various relatively independent functionalities, that can be enabled or disabled as required, also on a model-base. Imagine a simulation scenario where an industrial robot has to pick-up boxes and move them to another location; VREP computes the dynamics for grasping and holding the boxes and performs a kinematic simulation for the other parts of the cycle when dynamic effects are negligible. This approach makes it possible to calculate the industrial robot's movement quickly and precisely, which would not be the case had it been simulated entirely using complex dynamics libraries. This type of hybrid simulation is justified in this situation, if the robot is stiff and fixed and not otherwise influenced by its environment. In addition to adaptively enabling various of its functionalities in a selective manner, V-REP can also use them in a symbiotic manner, having one cooperate with another. In the case of a humanoid robot, for example, VREP can handle leg movements by (a) first calculating inverse kinematics for each leg (i.e., from a desired foot position and orientation, all leg joint positions are calculated); and then (b) assigning the calculated joint positions to be used as target joint positions by the dynamic's module. This allows specifying the humanoid motion in a very versatile way, since each foot would simply have to be assigned to follow a 6-dimensional path: the rest of calculations are automatically taken care of.

Simulation Environment and User Interface

A V-REP simulation scene, or simulation model contains several scene objects or elemental objects that are assembled in a tree-like hierarchy. The following scene objects are supported in V-REP:

- **Joints:** joints are elements that link two or more scene objects together with one to three degrees of freedom (prismatic, revolute, screw-like, or spherical). They can operate in various modes (e.g., force/torque mode, inverse kinematics mode, etc.)
- **Shapes:** shapes are triangular meshes, used for rigid body simulation and visualization. They can be optimized for fast dynamic collision response calculation, as a grouping of primitive or convex shapes. Other scene objects or calculation modules heavily rely on shapes for their calculations (proximity sensors, the dynamics module, or the mesh-mesh distance calculation module for example).
- **Proximity sensors:** they perform an exact minimum distance calculation to the part of a shape contained in a configurable detection volume, as opposed to simply performing detection based on rays. This results in a more continuous operation and thus, allows for more realistic simulation.
- **Vision sensors:** vision sensors allow to extract complex image information from a simulation scene (colors, object sizes, depth maps, etc.). A built-in filtering and image processing function enables the composition of blocks of filter elements.
- **Force sensors:** they represent rigid links between shapes, that can record applied forces and torques, and that can conditionally break apart when a given threshold is overshoot.
- **Graphs:** graphs can record a large variety of predefined or custom data streams. Data streams can then be displayed directly (time graph of a given data type), or combined with each other to display X/Y graphs, or 3D curves.
- **Cameras:** they allow scene visualization when associated with a viewport.
- **Lights:** lights illuminate a scene or individual scene objects, and directly influence cameras or vision sensors.
- **Paths:** they allow complex movement definitions in space (succession of freely combinable translations, rotations and/or pauses), and are used for guiding a welding robot's torch along a predefined trajectory, or for allowing conveyor belt movements for example.

- **Dummies:** a dummy is a reference frame, that can be used for various tasks, and is mainly used in conjunction with other scene objects, and as such, can be seen as a “helper.”
- **Mills:** they represent customizable convex volumes that can be used to simulate surface cutting operations on shapes (e.g., milling, laser cutting, etc.).

V-REP (CoppeliaSim) Modules: Scene objects are rarely used on their own, they rather operate on (or in conjunction with) other scene objects (e.g., a proximity sensor will detect shapes). In addition, V-REP offers several calculation modules that can directly operate on one or several scene objects. Following are the main *calculation modules*:

- **Kinematics module:** allows kinematics calculations (forward/inverse) for any type of mechanism (branched, closed, redundant, containing nested loops, etc.). The module is based on calculation of the damped least squares pseudoinverse. It supports conditional, damped/undamped, and weighted resolution.
- **Dynamics module:** allows handling rigid body dynamics calculation and interaction (collision response, grasping, etc.) via the Bullet Physics Library and the Open Dynamics Engine. Dynamics-based simulations still being in its infant shoes and often based on approximations, it is important to not only rely on one single physics engine, in order to validate results. At the time of writing, a third, high fidelity physics support via Vortex Dynamics is in preparation.
- **Collision detection module:** allows fast interference checking between any shape or collection of shapes. This module is fully independent from the collision response calculation algorithm of the dynamic’s module. It uses data structures based on a binary tree of oriented bounding boxes for accelerations.
- **Mesh-mesh distance calculation module:** allows fast minimum distance calculations between any shape (convex, concave, open, closed, etc.) or collection of shapes. The module uses the same data structures as the collision detection module. Additional optimization is also achieved with a temporal coherency caching technique.
- **Path/motion planning module:** handles holonomic path planning tasks and non-holonomic path planning tasks (for car-like vehicles) via an approach derived from the Rapidly-exploring Random Tree (RRT) algorithm. Path planning tasks of kinematic chains are also supported.

2. Car Introduction

A car or automobile is a motor vehicle with wheels. Most definitions of cars say that they run primarily on roads, seat one to eight people, have four wheels, and mainly transport people (rather than goods). We can use specific some equipment to design a Car for this simulation project. We have to add some extra vision and force sensors.

2.1 Car Components

1. Car Body: Car body is the main frame that holds all of the Components of the Car.
2. Universal Wheel: It's in the back of the Car.
3. Right Motor: To Rotate RIGHT Wheel.
4. Left Motor: To rotate LEFT wheel.
5. Right Wheel
6. Left Wheel
7. Vision Sensor (Right)
8. Vision Sensor (Left)
9. Vision Sensor: (Middle)

2.2 Car Functions:

Design and manufacture a four-wheel electric car. The car is required to follow the designated route on the ramp automatically. The car must run independently, No equipment can be used outside the vehicle (including power supply). The main function of the car is following the ramp on the wood route and turn according to the route on the wooden ramp. A ramp is made of wood panels about 1 m long and wide. Allow wood color and natural wood grain on the board. The surface of the wood work board is laid with 1 cm× cm black and white spaced note (hereinafter referred to as marking line) as route indication; The starting section of the mark line is a straight line, parallel to the sides of the board; At the top of the slope 90° , 20 cm; turning radius the parallel slope top distance ≥ 30 cm, ≤ 20 cm; from top of slope 1 m. in total length of marking line Parking marked 1 cm wide and 5 cm long black lines, perpendicular to the slope top marking line. The slope angle of the car and the top view of the driving line is shown in figure. The car mainly works on Microcontroller who controls all the operations. But there are some components like motor driver, power supply module and motor driver.

The car should travel at a uniform speed. After completing the ramp on the wooden route, the car marking point: the marking point of the car reaching the parking line itself-determined and clearly marked in the car before driving.

3. Algorithm

An algorithm is a set of commands that must be followed for a computer to perform calculations or other problem-solving operations. According to its formal definition, an algorithm is a finite set of instructions carried out in a specific order to perform a particular task. It is not the entire program or code; it is simple logic to a problem represented as an informal description in the form of a flowchart or pseudocode.

3.1 Car Control Algorithm & Car Tracing Algorithm

Case 1:

We'll be using a robot with 2 color sensors on each side. Alternatively, Light / Ultraviolet sensors can also work.

Steer the robot right (Left Image), Steer the robot left (Right Image)

In this case, only the right sensor (Sensor 2) or the left sensor (Sensor 1) detects a line a.k.a they detect black color.

If only the right sensor detects a black line, then the robot must steer right to follow the line. Alternatively, if only the left sensor detects a black line, then the robot must steer left to follow the line.

```
if right_sensor detects black
  // Move Right
  set left motor ON
  set right motor OFF
else if left_sensor detects black
  // Move Left
  set left motor OFF
  set right motor ON
endif
```

Case 2:

Keep the robot moving forward in the same direction

In this case, both the sensors do not detect a black line, so the robot should keep moving forward in the same direction and maintain its current journey path.

```
if right_sensor and left sensor do not detect black
set left motor ON
set right motor ON
```

Case 3:

Stop the robot (Left Image), Move forward (Right Image)

This case is a bit tricky. Depending on your game scenario, both the sensors detecting a black line could mean either it is a finish line (left image) or it is just a loop which is part of a bigger line-following problem (right image).

If it signifies a finish line, then the robot must stop and terminate the program. Otherwise, if it signifies a loop, then:

1. The robot should stop itself for a duration of 1–2 seconds to stabilize itself,
2. Move the robot a bit forward (approximately 1/4th of rotation) to move past the black line and then,
3. Continue the normal line following algorithm.

The significance of both the sensors detecting a black line has to be determined before the start of the program.

```
// Black line is the finish line
if left_sensor and right_sensor detect black
    set left motor OFF
    set right motor OFF// Black line is a part of a loop
if left_sensor and right_sensor detect black
    set both motors OFF for 2 seconds (Stabalise)
    set both motors ON for 1/4th rotation (Move past the
black line)
    continue to normal line-following algorithm
```

Complete Algorithm:

```
if right_sensor detects black
    // Move Right
    set left motor ON
    set right motor OFFelse if left_sensor detects black
    // Move Left
    set left motor OFF
    set right motor ONelse if right_sensor and left sensor
do not detect black
    set left motor ON
    set right motor ONelse if left_sensor and right_sensor
detect black
    set left motor OFF
    set right motor OFFendif
```

4. Experiments and Analysis

4.1 Parameters Setting

```
function sysCall_actuation()
  -- put your actuation code here
  v = 5
  dv = 8
  sim.setJointTargetVelocity(leftJoint,v)
  sim.setJointTargetVelocity(rightJoint,v)
  if (data_left~= nil) then
    intensity_left = data_left[11]
    intensity_right = data_right[11]
    if (intensity_right> 0.5 and intensity_left < 0.5) then
      print('turn right')
      sim.setJointTargetVelocity(rightJoint,v+dv)
    end
    if (intensity_left> 0.5 and intensity_right< 0.5) then
      print('turn left')
      sim.setJointTargetVelocity(leftJoint,v+dv)
    end
  end
end
end
```

```
function sysCall_sensing()
  -- put your sensing code here
  result,data_left=sim.readVisionSensor(leftSensor)
  result,data_right=sim.readVisionSensor(rightSensor)
  --print(result)
  -- if (data_left ~= nil) then
  --print('minimum:intensity,r,g,b,depth'..data_left[1]..' '..data_left[2] ..'
  '..data_left[3] ..' '..data_left[4] ..' '..data_left[5] )
  --print('maximum:intensity,r,g,b,depth'..data_left[6]..' '..data_left[7] ..'
  '..data_left[8] ..' '..data_left[9] ..' '..data_left[10] )
  print('left:average:intensity,r,g,b,depth'..data_left[11]..'
  '..data_left[12] ..' '..data_left[13] ..' '..data_left[14] ..' '..data_left[15] )
  print('right:average:intensity,r,g,b,depth'..data_right[11]..'
  '..data_right[12] ..' '..data_right[13] ..' '..data_right[14] ..'
  '..data_right[15] )
  print(' ')
  --end
end
```

Car Visual Parameters:

Line Tracer:

object alias: /Line Tracer (deprecated name: LineTracer)

object type: Shape (multishape, pure)

object position: x: -1.0802, y: +0.5742, z: +0.0277

object orientation: a: +090.14, b: -004.97, g: +089.98

Left Wheel Parameter:

object alias: /LineTracer/LeftWheel (deprecated name: LeftWheel)

object type: Shape (multishape, non-pure)

object position: x: -1.1419, y: +0.5351, z: +0.0270

object orientation: a: -158.75, b: +001.81, g: -175.38

Right Wheel Parameter:

object alias: /LineTracer/RightWheel (deprecated name: RightWheel)

object type: Shape (multishape, non-pure)

object position: x: -1.0263, y: +0.5250, z: +0.0270

object orientation: a: -158.75, b: +001.81, g: -175.38

Body Parameter:

object alias: /LineTracer/Body (deprecated name: Body)

object type: Shape (multishape, non-pure)

object position: x: -1.0802, y: +0.5742, z: +0.0207

object orientation: a: +000.14, b: +000.02, g: +085.03

Sensor Parameters:

Left Sensor:

object alias: /LineTracer/LeftSensor (deprecated name: LeftSensor)

object type: Vision sensor (sampling resolution: 16 x 16)

object position: x: -1.0954, y: +0.6600, z: +0.0184

object orientation: a: -179.86, b: +000.02, g: -175.03

Right Sensor:

object alias: /LineTracer/RightSensor (deprecated name: RightSensor)

object type: Vision sensor (sampling resolution: 16 x 16)

object position: x: -1.0505, y: +0.6561, z: +0.0184

object orientation: a: -179.86, b: +000.02, g: -175.03

Middle Sensor:

object alias: /LineTracer/MiddleSensor (deprecated name: MiddleSensor)

object type: Vision sensor (sampling resolution: 16 x 16)

object position: x: -1.0729, y: +0.6581, z: +0.0184

object orientation: a: -179.86, b: +000.02, g: -175.03

Path Parameters:

object alias: /Path (deprecated name: Path)

object type: Dummy

object position: x: +0.00000001, y: -0.0500, z: +0.0000

object orientation: a: -000.00, b: +000.00, g: -000.00

4.2 Result Analysis

```
turn right
left:average:intensity,r,g,b,depth0.57254904508591 0.59607845544815 0.580392181873
32 0.54509806632996 0.1364359408617
right:average:intensity,r,g,b,depth0.69411766529083 0.71372550725937 0.69803923368
454 0.6745098233223 0.15134163200855
```

Right Turn

```
turn left
left:average:intensity,r,g,b,depth0.73725491762161 0.76078432798386 0.741176486015
32 0.72156864404678 0.15571124851704
right:average:intensity,r,g,b,depth0.54901963472366 0.56470590829849 0.54901963472
366 0.53725492954254 0.13067112863064
```

Left Turn

5. Summary:

Advantages of Line Following Robot:

1. Robot movement is automatic
2. It is used for long distance applications
3. Simplicity of building
4. Fit and forget system
5. Used in home, industrial automations etc.

The line following robot is one of the self-operating robots. That detects and follows a line drawn on the area. The line is indicated by white line on a black surface or black line on a white surface. This system must be sense by the line. This application is depending upon the sensors.

Project Screenshots:

Working Anyhow

Scene hierarchy (scene 1)

- DefaultCamera
- XYZCameraProxy
- DefaultLights
- Floor
- LineTracer
 - DynamicLeftJoint
 - LeftJoint
 - LeftWheel
 - DynamicRightJoint
 - RightJoint
 - RightWheel
 - sensor
 - DynamicSlider
 - Body
 - LineTracerBase
 - LeftSensor
 - RightSensor
 - MiddleSensor
- Path
 - ctrlP[0]
 - ctrlP[1]
 - ctrlP[2]
 - ctrlP[3]
 - ctrlP[4]
 - ctrlP[5]

Selected objects: 0
Simulation time: 00:00:00.00 (at 50.0 ms/pp/1)

/LineTracer/RightSensor

/LineTracer/MiddleSensor

/LineTracer/LeftSensor

[sandboxScript:info] Simulation suspended.

Input Lua code here, or type "help()" (use TAB for auto-completion)

Sandbox script

Working Anyhow

Scene hierarchy (scene 1)

- DefaultCamera
- XYZCameraProxy
- DefaultLights
- Floor
- LineTracer
 - DynamicLeftJoint
 - LeftJoint
 - LeftWheel
 - DynamicRightJoint
 - RightJoint
 - RightWheel
 - sensor
 - DynamicSlider
 - Body
 - LineTracerBase
 - LeftSensor
 - RightSensor
 - MiddleSensor
- Path
 - ctrlP[0]
 - ctrlP[1]
 - ctrlP[2]
 - ctrlP[3]
 - ctrlP[4]
 - ctrlP[5]

Selected objects: 0
Simulation time: 00:00:00.10 (at 50.0 ms/pp/1)
Simulation script called: 5 (16 ms)
Proximity sensor handling enabled: Calculations: 0, detections: 0 (0 ms)
Vision sensor handling enabled (FBO): Calculations: 3, detections: 1 (11 ms)
Dynamic handling enabled (Bullet 2.76): Calculation passes: 10 (2 ms)

/LineTracer/RightSensor

/LineTracer/MiddleSensor

/LineTracer/LeftSensor

turn left

Input Lua code here, or type "help()" (use TAB for auto-completion)

Sandbox script

Suspend simulation

References:

No need any references!

[THE END OF THE PROJECT]